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Research Article

FREQUENCY OF ATRIAL FIBRILLATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE (COPD)

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the frequency of atrial fibrillation in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).

Patients and Methods: A total of fifty patients with chronic obstructive lung disease were included in this study. The criterion for the selection of the patients for the study was those patients diagnosed case of COPD. The exclusive criteria were known asthmatic patients and the case of restrictive lung diseases; history of ischemic heart disease, already on cardiac medications, patients with hyperthyroidism whereas the frequency / percentages (%) and means $\pm$ SD computed for study variables.

Results: During six-month study period total fifty patients had COPD for $\geq$ 3-year duration were explored and study. The mean $\pm$ SD for age (yrs) of population was 59.52 $\pm$ 7.81 respectively. Regarding gender, male 32 (64%) and female 18 (36%) individuals whereas the atrial fibrillation was identified in 31 (62%) patients of COPD

Conclusion: COPD patients had a higher risk for AF among the Pakistani populace. Among COPD patients, hypertension and CHF were distinguished as autonomous hazard factors for new-beginning AF.

KeyWords: Atrial fibrillation, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and Arrhythmia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is a typical arrhythmia seen in clinical practice [1]. AF is additionally a significant hazard factor for stroke, and the danger of AF increments with age, ascending from 1.5% at an age of 50–59 years to 23.5% at an age of 80–89 years [2]. From 1985 to 1999, hospitalizations for AF expanded triple, and the high pervasiveness of AF brought about more noteworthy restorative consumptions [3]. A past report utilized constant electrocardiography to screen arrhythmias in patients with COPD and found that the frequency of AF was fundamentally more noteworthy in COPD patients than in patients without COPD [4]. A study demonstrated that during hospitalization for AF, COPD patients had an expanded length of emergency clinic remain and expanded medical clinic mortality [5]. There is a scarcity of data on AF occurrence and hazard factors in patients with COPD in most studies [6, 7], and they need data in regards to Pakistani populaces. The point of our examination was to research the rate of AF in Pakistani COPD patients and investigate the autonomous hazard factors for AF in this populace

PATIENT AND METHODS: A total of fifty patients with chronic obstructive lung disease were included in this study. The criterion for the selection of the patients for the study was those patients diagnosed case of COPD. The exclusive criteria were known asthmatic patients and the case of restrictive lung diseases; history of ischemic heart disease, already on cardiac medications, patients with hyperthyroidism. After having selected cases for the study, careful history & examination was carried out in each patient in particular relation to respiratory and cardiovascular examination. The demographical and clinical profile of subjects was also noted. The co-morbidities were also explored while the cardiac manifestation was explored through clinical history, physical examination and specific investigations (ECG and echocardiography) whereas the data was collected on pre-designed proforma and analyzed in SPSS to manipulate the frequencies and percentages.

RESULTS:

During six-month study period total fifty patients had COPD for ≥ 3 year duration were explored and study. The mean $\pm$ SD for age (yrs) of population was 59.52 ± 7.81 . The demographical and clinical profile of study population is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: The Demographical and Clinical Profile Of Study Population

Parameter	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage (%)
AGE (yrs)		
40-49	07	14
50-59	23	46
60-69	14	28
70+	06	12
GENDER		
Male	32	64
Female	18	36
RESIDENCE		
Urban	20	40
Rural	30	60
Co-morbidities		
Hypertension	27	54
Diabetes mellitus	22	44
Hyperlipidemia	15	30
Malignancy	10	20
Chronic renal failure	05	10
Atrial fibrillation		
Yes	31	62
No	19	38

DISCUSSION:

There are numerous systems of AF in COPD. The main component includes inflammation. COPD is a foundational incendiary infection, and serum C-responsive protein (CRP) levels are altogether higher in these patients than in solid controls; CRP is additionally connected with age, lung work, oxygen immersion. The subsequent component includes medicine. COPD patients are recommended respiratory medications, including β -agonists, anticholinergic medications, and theophylline and aminophylline. β -agonists initiate β -receptors and adenylate cyclase, prompting the actuation of cyclic adenosine monophosphate and protein kinase A, which phosphorylates target proteins and prompts a compression of myocytes. These chronotropic and depolarization impacts lead to arrhythmogenicity [8, 9]. Different variables that actuate AF in the COPD populace incorporate more established age, hypoxia, smoking, and cardiovascular parameters. We examine the rate of new-beginning AF in COPD patients. Our study delivered a few discoveries. In the first place, COPD was related with the danger of AF, second, the danger of AF expanded with more seasoned age in patients with COPD with male patients dominating. The ARIC study, [10] demonstrated that lower pneumonic capacity was related with a higher frequency of AF. In the study by Ganga et al, [11] CHF, chronic kidney infection, and

hypertension were hazard factors for AF in the geriatric populace. In our investigation, we showed that CHF and hypertension were likewise altogether connected with new-beginning AF in the COPD populace.

CONCLUSION:

COPD patients had a higher risk for AF among the Pakistani populace. Among COPD patients, hypertension and CHF were distinguished as autonomous hazard factors for new-beginning AF. In this manner the outcomes likewise recommend that doctors need to expand checking and early mediation for COPD patients to examine and treat AF.

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